

A new glyceride from *Xylocarpus molluccensis* fruits

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Abstract : Ethanol extract of the fruits of the plant showed promising antidiabetic activity as well as very good antidyslipidemic activity in experimental animals. Further fractionation of the ethanol extract in four fractions, the activity was localized in the chloroform fraction. Therefore to explore the active constituents, a detailed chemical investigation have been taken. Total 12 compounds have been isolated and characterized from the all fractions and out of 12 compounds, 4 compounds were isolated from the active chloroform fraction and a new diglyceride has been isolated and characterized from the hexane fraction of the ethanol extract. The activity of this plant will be reported separately.

Keywords : *Xylocarpus molluccensis*, fruits, new diglyceride.

Introduction

With a view to explore the possibilities of finding new molecules, with proven therapeutic efficacy for human use, a programme is in operation at the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow (India) for the screening of extracts of marine organisms for a wide range of biological activities. The programme consists of collection, identification and extraction of marine flora and fauna found along the Indian coasts for biological screening. With an aim to isolate the bioactive compounds from the fruits of *Xylocarpus molluccensis*, it was selected for a detailed chemical and biological investigation. *Xylocarpus molluccensis* is a mangrove plant and belongs to the family Meliaceae¹. It occurs around the littoral of the tropical Indian Ocean and extends up to the Pacific Islands². The genus *Xylocarpus* occurs in the coastal area of Andaman and Nicobar Islands and Sunderban in India. It is a small (6–10 m tall) and less branched mangrove. The bark pressings of *X. molluccensis* are used in cholera and fever³. The fruits of *X. molluccensis* are used as aphrodisiac³. The kernels are used in tonics and in relieving colic. The seeds or peels of the fruits are utilized as a poultice for swellings and ash of the seeds is applied to itch⁴. The fruits are used as a cure for swellings of the

breast and in elephantiasis also. On reviewing the literature, the compounds isolated from the genus *Xylocarpus* were limonoids. Most of these limonoids from *X. molluccensis* were the xylocensins. Xylomollin^{5,6} and a phenyl keto acid⁷.

Results and discussion

A pure compound XM-1 was obtained from the hexane fraction of the crude extract of the fruits of *X. molluccensis*, and it was crystallized from ethyl acetate as white solid, m.p. 110–112 °C. ESMS of the XM-1 displayed the molecular ion peak at m/z 708 $[M+Na+H]^+$ suggesting the molecular mass to be 684 $[M]^+$. The molecular mass 684 was in agreement with NMR data and elemental analysis. The IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 2925, 1460 cm^{-1} (aliphatic C–H stretching), 1730, 1240 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl) suggesting it as fatty ester. The absorption band at 3400 cm^{-1} indicated the presence of hydroxyl group.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of XM-1 showed a broad singlet at δ 1.25 attributed to aliphatic methylene protons of a long fatty chain, a triplet at δ 2.34 (J 6.5 Hz) integrating for four protons assignable to the methylene protons attached to the ester carbonyl supporting the presence of

fatty ester. Any terminal primary methyl group was absent. The ^1H NMR spectrum further showed three envelopes of protons at δ 4.10 (m) integrating for one proton, δ 4.16 (m) integrating for two protons and at 4.20 (m) integrating for two protons due to carbinol protons of glycerol moiety. Absence of a multiplet integrating for one proton at δ 5.28 and the presence of H-2 as an up field one-proton multiplet at δ 4.10 indicated that the hydroxyl group at carbon C-2 of glycerol moiety was not esterified. The ^1H NMR also showed another triplet at δ 4.05 (J 6.9 Hz) integrating for four protons. Absence of any triplet at δ 0.88 indicated the absence of any terminal methyl groups and presence of some other functional group in the fatty chains. Instead, a singlet integrating for six protons at δ 2.04 was present assignable to two acetoxy methyl protons.

In the ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of the XM-1, the protons at δ 4.10 (H-2) showed correlation with the resonances at δ 4.16 and δ 4.20 attributed to H_2 -1 and H_2 -3. The multiplet at δ 4.05 did not show correlation with the proton signals of the glycerol moiety. This indicated that the protons at δ 4.05 are present at some isolated position in the long chain fatty acyl moiety. The multiplet at δ 4.05 showed correlation with acetoxy methyl singlet at δ 2.04 showing that an acetate group is present in the fatty acyl chain. The multiplet at δ 4.05 showed correlation with the methylene protons at δ 1.61, which then showed cross peak with the large broad singlet at δ 1.25, attributed to the long chain aliphatic methylene protons. This confirmed the position of the protons at δ 4.05 in the fatty chain of the XM-1.

The ^{13}C NMR spectral data of the XM-1 showed low field carbon resonances at δ 171.5 (two ester carbonyls), δ 174.5 (two ester carbonyls), δ 68.7 (oxymethine), δ 65.3 (two oxymethylene carbons) due to glycerol moiety. Many carbon signals appeared between δ 29.3–29.8 (aliphatic methylene carbons indicative of the presence of long chain acyl moiety). The ^{13}C NMR also showed another carbon resonance at δ 64.9 attributed to two oxymethylene carbons. Two acetoxy methyl resonances were shown at δ 21.4. Since the terminal methyl groups were absent in the spectra of the XM-1, the hydroxyl groups present at the C-1 and C-2 positions were esterified by long chain fatty acids having a terminal hydroxyl group esterified by acetic acid as indicated by the ^1H - ^1H

COSY spectrum further confirmed by other 2D-experiments.

The XM-1 formed monoacetate on treatment with acetic anhydride in pyridine kept overnight. The acetate of the compound showed molecular ion peak at m/z 750 $[\text{M}+\text{Na}+\text{H}]^+$. The formation of monoacetate confirmed that the XM-1 has one hydroxyl group free and hence the XM-1 is a diglyceride.

The HMQC and HMBC spectral data of the XM-1 gave further information about the correlations of protons. In the HMQC spectrum, the two proton multiplet at δ 4.16 showed cross peak with the methylene carbon at δ 65.3 attributed to H_2 -1 and C-1 respectively. The one proton multiplet at δ 4.10 was correlated to the methine carbon at δ 68.7 and assigned as H-2 and C-2 respectively. The two proton multiplet at δ 4.20 showed cross peak with the methylene carbon δ 65.3 (C-3), hence attributed to H_2 -3. The singlet at δ 2.04 (H_3 -18' and H_3 -18'') was correlated to the methyl carbon at δ 21.4 (C-18' and C-18'') attributed to be two acetoxy methyls. The multiplet at δ 4.05 correlated to the methylene carbon at δ 64.9 and the acetoxy methyl correlated with the triplet at δ 4.05 indicating the presence of the acetate groups in the fatty chains. The two proton multiplet at δ 1.61 was correlated with the methylene carbon at δ 28.1 and the multiplet at δ 1.62 was correlated with δ 25.1. The triplet at δ 2.34 showed cross peak with the methylene carbon at δ 34.3 and the multiplet at δ 1.26 showed cross peak with the methylene carbon at δ 26.1. The HMBC spectrum showed the signal at δ 4.20 (H_2 -1) showed cross peak with the carbon signals at δ 68.7 (C-2) and δ 65.3 (C-3). The multiplet at δ 4.10 (H-2) showed correlation with the carbon signal at δ 65.3 (C-3 and C-1) and the multiplet at δ 4.16 (H-1) showed cross peak with the carbon resonance at δ 68.7 (C-2) and 65.3 (C-3). These multiple bond correlations confirmed the presence of glycerol moiety in the compound. The two-methyl protons at δ 2.04 (H_3 -18' and H_3 -18'') showed cross peak with the ester carbonyl carbon at δ 171.5 (C-17' and C-17'') and the methylene carbons at δ 64.9 (C-16' and C-16''). This showed the presence of $\text{CH}_2\text{-O-COCH}_3$ moiety in the compound. The protons attached to one of the carbons at δ 64.9 resonating at δ 4.05 correlated with the methylenes of the aliphatic chain at δ 28.9 (C-15' and C-15'') and δ 26.1 (C-14' and C-14'') as revealed in the HMBC spectrum. Hence,

the fatty chain ends in a $\text{CH}_2\text{-O-COCH}_3$ terminus supported by the fact that any terminal methyl was absent in the spectra of the XM-1. Previously, no such diglyceride has been reported in the literature in which the fatty acyl chains end in acetoxyl group. Rather, a number of diglycerides have been reported²³ with normal fatty acyl chain having terminal methyl group.

The ^1H NMR spectrum of acetate showed four sets of carbinol protons at δ 4.20 (dd, J 6.5, 11.5 Hz) and δ 4.29 (dd, J 6.5, 11.5 Hz) integrating for two protons each attributed to H_2 -1 and H_2 -3 methylene protons of the glycerol moiety, δ 5.25 integrating for one proton attributed to H-2 of the glycerol moiety and a triplet at δ 4.05 (J 6.8 Hz) integrating for four protons. The chemical shift of the triplet at δ 4.05 did not change after acetylation. This confirms that the protons at δ 4.05 are not present in the vicinity of the free hydroxyl group of the glycerol moiety and attributed to the methylene protons (H-16' and H-16'') adjacent to the acetate groups of the fatty acyl chains. A two-proton triplet at δ 2.31 (J 7.4 Hz) was assigned to the methylene protons adjacent to the ester carbonyls groups at C-1 and C-3. The three acetoxyl methyl protons were observed as singlets at δ 2.04 (6H) and δ 2.07 (3H). A broad singlet at δ 1.25 was assigned to the aliphatic methylene protons of the long chain hydroxy fatty acid (Fig. 2).

The ^1H - ^1H COSY spectrum of the acetate of the XM-1 showed correlation between the multiplet at δ 5.25 and δ 4.12 assigned to H-2 and H_2 -1 respectively. H-2 also showed cross peak with the resonance at δ 4.25 assigned to H_2 -3. The signal at δ 4.05 showed correlation with the resonance at δ 1.61 assignable to H_2 -15' and H-15'' which was then correlated to the protons at δ 1.26 assigned to H_2 -14' and H_2 -14''. The H_2 -14' and 14'' were then correlated to the aliphatic methylene protons of the long chain fatty acid moiety. Similarly, the protons at δ 2.31 showed cross peak with δ 1.62 assigned to H_2 -3' and 3'' methylene protons.

From the above data the structure of the XM-1 was assigned as a diglyceride having long chain fatty acid ester at C-1 and C-3. In the literature, the closest derivative of this compound is glycerol 1,3-dipalmitate⁸ from a sea urchin *Temnopleurus toreumaticus*. On comparison of the spectroscopic data⁸, it was found that the triplet due to the terminal methyl group in the ^1H NMR of the

glycerol 1,3-dipalmitate was absent in that of the compound XM-1. Similarly, no methyl carbon resonance was present in ^{13}C NMR and DEPT spectra of the compound XM-1, but it was present in that of glycerol 1,3-dipalmitate. Instead, the ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectra of the compound XM-1 exhibited the presence of acetoxyl groups that were shown to be present at the terminus of the fatty acyl chains shown by the HMBC correlations as discussed previously. Thus, the structure of the compound is confirmed as shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1. XM-1.

Fig. 2. HMBC correlations of the XM-1.

This is the first report of a diglyceride with terminal acetoxyl groups in the fatty acyl chains. The other 11 known compounds were identified as xylocensin-E⁹, xylocensin-I¹⁰, xylocensin-J¹¹, xylocensin X and Y¹², friedelin²⁴, palmitic acid, dibutylphthalate, sitosterol, β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside and sucrose by comparisons of the spectral data of those compounds reported in the literature.

Experimental

Collection of plant material :

Fruits of the *Xylocarpus molluccensis* mangrove were collected by the Botany Division, Central Drug Research Institute from South Andaman Coast in the month of March. Specimen sample (voucher specimen number 424) has been identified and preserved in the herbarium of the Botany Division of the Institute, Lucknow, India. Fruits were shade dried and epicarp from the fruits were separated.

Extraction fractionation and isolation of compounds :

Air dried powdered epicarp (2.0 kg) were placed in

glass percolator filled with 95% ethanol 5.0 L and allowed to stand overnight at room temperature, the percolate was collected and the process of extraction was repeated four times. The combined extracts were filtered, concentrated under reduced pressure below 50 °C to minimum volume of 1.0 L. It was further dried in hot air vacuum oven at 50 °C to brown powder (58.4 g). The brown powder was suspended in water (70 ml) and fractionated in to hexane soluble fraction (1.9 g), which was crystallized from ethyl acetate (90 mg).

We have chemically analyzed all the fractions in the quest to isolate the new molecules. On repeated chromatography (Column, PLC and HPLC) the hexane fraction yielded a new glyceride which was crystallized from ethyl acetate (90 mg) along with palmitic acid, β -sitosterol, friedelin¹³ and dibutyl phthalate. The chloroform fraction on chemical purification yielded known xylocensins (xylocensin-E¹⁰, xylocensin-I¹¹, xylocensin-J¹¹ and xylocensins X+Y¹² and from the butanol fraction only free sugars glucose, sucrose and β -sitosterol- β -D-glucoside could be isolated and characterized.

Physicochemical characteristics of the compound XM-1 (diglyceride) :

It was obtained as a white flaky solid from methanol, m.p. 110–112 °C. It analyzed for C₃₉H₇₂O₉, Found : C, 68.04; H, 9.45. Required for C₃₉H₇₂O₉ : C, 68.38; H, 10.59%. Its infrared spectrum showed absorption peaks at 3400, 2925, 1460, 1730, 1240 cm⁻¹. It showed molecular ion peak at *m/z* 708 [M+Na+H]⁺ in its ESIMS spectra. The ¹H and ¹³C NMR data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. ¹H NMR spectral data of compound new diglyceride (300 MHz, CDCl₃)

Position	δ_H	Multiplicity
Glycerol moiety		
H ₂ -1	4.20	dd (<i>J</i> 6.5, 11.5 Hz)
H-2	5.25	m
H ₂ -3	4.29	dd (<i>J</i> 6.5, 11.5 Hz)
Acyl moiety		
2' and 2''	2.31	t (<i>J</i> 7.4 Hz)
3' and 3''	1.62	m
2-OCOCH ₃	2.07	s
Aliphatic methylene groups	1.25	br s
H ₂ -15' and 15''	1.61	m
H ₂ -16' and 16''	4.05	t (<i>J</i> 6.8 Hz)
Terminal OCOCH ₃ (H ₃ -18' and 18'')	2.04	s

Table 2. ¹H-¹H correlations spectral data of compound new diglyceride acetate (300 MHz, CDCl₃)

¹ H- ¹ H correlations (δ)	Assignments
4.20 and 5.25	H ₂ -1 and H-2
4.29 and 5.25	H ₂ -9 and H-2
4.05 and 2.04	H ₂ -16', 16'' and H ₃ -18', 18''
4.05 and 1.61	H ₂ -16', 16'' and H ₂ -15', 15''
1.61 and 1.25	H ₂ -15', 15'' and aliphatic methylene protons
2.34 and 1.62	H ₂ -2', 2'' and H ₂ -3', 3''
1.62 and 1.25	H ₂ -2', 2'' and aliphatic methylene protons

Table 3. ¹H-¹³C (HMBC) long range correlations spectral data of compound new diglyceride (300 MHz, CDCl₃)

δ_H	HMBC correlations (δ_C)	Assignments
4.16 (H ₂ -1)	65.3, 68.7, 174.1	C-3, C-2, C-1'
4.10 (H-2)	65.3 (2C)	C-1 and C-2
4.20 (H ₂ -3)	65.3, 68.7, 174.1	C-1, C-2, C-1''
2.34 (H ₂ -2' and 2'')	25.1, 29.5, 174.1	C-3',3''; C-4'-13', 4''-13''; C-1',1''
1.62 (H ₂ -3' and 3'')	29.5, 34.3	C-4'-13', 4''-13''; C-2',2''
1.61 (H ₂ -15' and 15'')	26.1, 29.5, 64.9	C-14',14''; C-4'-13', 4''-13''; C-16',16''
4.05 (H ₂ -16' and 16'')	26.1, 28.8, 171.4	C-14',14''; C-15', 15''; C-17',17''
2.04 (H ₃ -18' and 18'')	171.4, 64.9	C-17',17''; C-16',16''

Conclusions

The new glyceride isolated from *X. molluccensis* did not show the antidiabetic effect in experimental rats. Therefore further structure modification is required to get some antidiabetic active molecules.

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